

UTILIZATION OF VIRTUAL LEARNING APPLICATIONS FOR E-LEARNING DELIVERY IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract: The study examined the utilization of virtual learning applications for e-learning delivery in public universities in Enugu State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study was 5437 which comprised 839 academic staff and 4598 final year students in University of Nigeria, Nsukka and Enugu State University of Science and Technology, ESUT. The sample for the study was 523 respondents which comprised 75 lecturers and 448 final year students. The instrument for data collection was a researcher structured questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three research specialists. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, it was trial tested on 12 lecturers and 28 students in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka in Anambra State. To ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument, the researcher used Cronbach alpha statistic. The computation yielded .79 for cluster 1, .82 for cluster 2. The instrument had an overall reliability index of .81 which indicated that the instrument was reliable and, therefore, was used for data collection in this study. The researcher used frequency and percentages to answer research question 1, but used mean scores and standard deviations to answer research questions 2-5. The null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic at .05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that virtual learning applications are not adequately made available for the lecturers and students' utilization for e-learning delivery in public universities and the respondents viewed the integration of virtual learning applications into instructional planning in public universities positively. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended that Universities management should provide comprehensive training sessions for lecturers and students on utilizing virtual learning applications effectively.

Keywords: Virtual Learning, e- learning, Teaching, public universities, utilize

INTRODUCTION

The transformation in education has resulted in a fundamental change from a focus on the teacher to a focus on the learner. This means that educators no longer dictate what and how students should learn; instead, the interests of the learners determine the direction of their learning, primarily due to the availability of the Internet. However, the utilization of the Internet in education has become the prevailing trend in 2023 (Hoti & Shatri,

2023). It was initially adopted out of necessity in 2020 when the global Covid-19 pandemic forced people into home quarantine, affecting the entire world.

The Covid-19 pandemic has highlighted the significant advantages of distance learning, particularly learning from home. Ziaul-Hoq (2020), noted that the pandemic made a profound impact on students' lives, challenging their adaptability and flexibility in response to a major global crisis. As a result, Ziaul-Hoq (2020), posited that more than 1,524,648,768 students were unable to physically attend schools. In response to this situation, virtual learning emerged as an alternative method to ensure uninterrupted education. Since the pandemic's onset, virtual learning and other similar approaches have been employed to maintain continuity in education.

Virtual learning refers to an educational approach that goes beyond traditional classroom settings by leveraging internet resources, platforms, satellite connections, and other related systems. It allows individuals to access, analyze, create, exchange, and utilize data, information, and knowledge in ways that were previously difficult to imagine. In accordance with Tata (2016), virtual education broadens the horizons of learning by utilizing electronic tools like instant messaging, blogs, peer-to-peer technology, flash applications, downloads, wikis, reputation systems, microfiches, chat rooms, camera phones, Google, and web browsing.

Ezenwafor and Nwachukwu (2020) highlighted that the global transformation in various aspects of life has given rise to new trends like e-business, e-office, and e-learning, which are being employed to address diverse human problems. The emergence of e-learning has led to the adoption of new methods for teaching and learning different subjects in schools. Electronic learning utilizes interactive technologies and communication systems to enhance the learning process, presenting opportunities for a significant transformation in teaching and learning methods. Initially, e-learning was often equated with distance education, where learning solely occurred through web-based platforms. It was also seen as a technical improvement or support for online education. However, there emerged a need to purposefully design educational courses and adapt them for virtual learning environments. Despite its existence for some time, e-learning is still a relatively new pedagogical approach, with varying definitions and significance among different scholars and researchers. It can be delivered in real-time, allowing for interactive participation, or through pre-recorded lectures for instructional purposes.

Meanwhile, the utilization of virtual learning applications in public universities in Enugu State cannot only address various educational challenges but also enhance the quality, accessibility, and reach of higher education. It represents a forward-thinking approach that can benefit both students and institutions in the pursuit of academic excellence. In recent years, there has been a global shift towards e-learning, accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Public universities in Enugu State need to keep up with this trend to remain competitive on a national and international standard. Understanding the utilization of virtual learning applications is crucial to ensure that universities in the state are not left behind in this educational revolution. It is based on the above background that the present study examined the utilization of virtual learning applications for e-learning delivery in public universities in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

The use of virtual learning applications in delivering e-learning in public universities in Enugu State is encountering obstacles that hinder its effective utilization. These obstacles encompass insufficient infrastructure, limited device accessibility, and a gap in technical knowledge and skills. Both students and

lecturers frequently lack the necessary expertise to navigate and utilize virtual learning applications efficiently, which hampers their full engagement with e-learning platforms. Certain stakeholders, such as lecturers and administrators, may exhibit resistance towards adopting virtual learning applications due to their unfamiliarity with them or a preference for traditional teaching methods. This resistance can obstruct the successful implementation of e-learning initiatives.

In Nigeria, particularly in public universities in Enugu State, lecturers encounter significant challenges in utilizing e-learning due to inadequate ICT infrastructure. These challenges include a shortage of essential resources such as computers, computer laboratories, internet and email facilities, videophone systems, teleconferencing devices, wireless applications, digital libraries, digital classrooms, and multimedia systems. Many lecturers find it difficult to incorporate e-learning into their instructional delivery, largely due to the high costs of ICT infrastructure and maintenance, insufficient funding for e-learning development, a preference for traditional teaching methods, and a lack of ICT skills among lecturers. Consequently, this study explores the utilization of virtual learning applications for e-learning in public universities in Enugu State.

The purpose of the study was to examine the utilization of virtual learning applications in e-learning delivery in public universities in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to examine the:

1. virtual learning applications that are adequately made available for the lecturers and students' utilization for e-learning delivery in public universities;
2. perceptions of lecturers and students regarding the integration of available virtual learning applications into instructional planning for students' degree programmes in public universities;

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Virtual Learning Applications

The present computer and communication technologies have been effectively applied in various fields, but their potential for delivering widespread instruction to students is not fully exploited (Ellsworth, 2014). The emerging technologies allow students and instructors to interact without significant limitations of time or place. Additionally, the current technologies have the capacity to create a flexible and affordable learning environment. This endeavour aims to establish an economical teaching model known as the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), as a step in that direction.

Godvinsamy (2017) outlined five distinct characteristics of virtual learning that set it apart from other forms of learning. These include its web-based nature, the presence of a virtual classroom, the ability to personalize the curriculum, the availability of diverse learning experiences, and the presence of measurable outcomes. Logan (2011), virtual learning encompasses various technologies such as inter-, intra-, and extranets, audio or video conferencing, television, video, satellites, DVD, and mobile phones. These technologies indicate that there is a physical separation between the learner and the instructor, with technology playing a role in the learning process.

Virtual Learning

Virtual learning involves acquiring knowledge through interactions with digitally delivered content, network-based services, and tutoring support. It utilizes various online tools and media, including the Internet, intranets, extranets, simulations, games, virtual worlds, clouds, satellite broadcasts, and web platforms. Olibie, Ezoem and Ekene (2014), have explored the application of these technologies within the context of virtual education. Olibie, Ezoem and Ekene (2014), further stated that electronic forms of communication, such as email, web portals, downloadable executable files, social media platforms like Facebook, web-based systems, digital theses, and electronic portfolios, are seamlessly incorporated into the realm of online learning experiences.

University Education

The word “University” is derived from the Latin expression; Universitas magisterium et scholium, which roughly means “community of teachers and scholars”, or the union of scholars (Jones 2022). University is the highest level of education where the high level manpower, intellectual and future leaders are developed. It is a place where students come together to pursue knowledge and it promotes the development of intellectual capacities of individuals to understand and appreciate their environments (Ajayi, 2013). Universities therefore educate future leaders and develop the high-level technical capacities that underpin economic growth and development (Odekunle, 2011).

University education is at the centre of human resource development and advancement. Idikwu (2014), a university is a well-defined and structured establishment known all over the world as the highest educational institution for the recognition of academic excellence. Idoko (2015) was of the view that a university is an acclaimed centre of excellence where intellectual cross fertilization of ideas systematically takes place, all geared towards the development of the individual intellectual capacity, resourcefulness and character moulding for overall societal advancement in all fields of enquiry.

Concept of E-learning

E-learning as a sub-system within ICT, is the electronic process which enhances the delivery and administration of learning opportunities and support via computer, networked and web-based technology to help individual performance and development. E-learning, according to (Amer, 2014) is defined as “a process of teaching and learning using electronic media, including computers and its various software, networks, the internet, electronic libraries, and others. It can be defined as providing the circular content and what it contains like explanations, exercises, and interaction partial or complete follow-up in the classroom or remotely by means of advanced programs which are stored in the computer on the internet. E-learning which includes the usage of computer technology as a means of running regular academic activities is fast gaining recognition nearly in every society (Olowonisi, 2016). Ibezim (2013), earlier highlighted that e-learning has in essence become one of such tools that is being frequently used to enhance teaching and learning in the 21st century.

Utilization of Virtual Learning Applications

Utilization of virtual learning applications depends on its level of awareness and the readiness of both lecturers and students to utilize it effectively in teaching and learning process. Ipaye (2011), lists some of these tools for virtual learning to include websites, wikis, blogs, Second Life, e-mail, twitters, Course Management systems,

video/audio podcasts, Facebook, threaded discussion lists, video/audio text chat, and videoconferences software. Jackson (2013) viewed e-learning resources as technology-aided learning tools that blend both online and face-to-face learning approaches which include hard and software components like internet, video conferencing, mobile technologies, CD/DVD, electronic learning platforms and their likes. Udegbumam (2016) maintained that e-learning resources consist of electronic media and devices used as tools for ameliorating access to training, communication and interaction which adopts new ways to understand and develop learning.

Technology Acceptance Theory (TAT)

The Technology Acceptance Theory was propounded by Davis in 1989. The theory suggests that when users are presented with a new technology like virtual learning applications, a number of factors influence their decision about how and when they will use it. The central idea behind the Technology Acceptance theory is that a user intention to use a technology is determined by his/her perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use of the technology.

Notably, perceived usefulness (PU) which is the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system, like virtual learning applications, would enhance his or her job performance; and perceived ease-of-use (PEU) which is the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system like virtual learning applications would be free from effort. TAT proposes that perceived ease-of- use and perceived usefulness of technology such as virtual learning applications are predictors of user attitude towards using the technology, subsequent behavioural intentions and actual usage. TAT is an intention-based model developed specifically for explaining and/or predicting user acceptance of computer technology such as virtual learning applications.

Technology acceptance theory is relevant to this study because it helps the lecturers and students to understand how they accept and adopt virtual learning technologies which can ultimately impact their usage and effectiveness. By applying the principles of TAT, universities can gain insights into the factors influencing the acceptance and utilization of virtual learning applications. This knowledge can guide the development, implementation, and continuous improvement of these technologies, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness of virtual learning experiences for students and lecturers alike.

The technology acceptance theory focuses on the individual's acceptance and adoption of technology, particularly their attitudes, intentions, and perceived usefulness and ease of use of the technology but failed to take cognizance of the broader context of social learning and behaviour change. This is the rationale for which the Social Cognitive Theory propounded by Bandura in 1986 becomes critical in this study.

Empirical Studies

In this section, the researcher examined different studies carried out by other researchers that are related to this study. Some of the studies are reviewed as follows:

Ile and Alonta (2019) conducted a study on extent of utilization of e-learning resources by business education students in public tertiary institutions in Enugu State, Nigeria. One research question was posed and two hypotheses tested. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. A total of 1407 business education students in four public tertiary institutions in Enugu State made up the population of the study, out of

which 312 students were used as sample. The findings of the study revealed among others that business education students in public tertiary institutions utilized e-learning resources for research purposes to a high extent.

Ezenwafor and Nwachukwu (2020) conducted a study on the extent of utilization of e-learning resources for instructional delivery by Office Technology and Management lecturers in polytechnics in South-East Nigeria. Findings revealed that the lecturers rarely utilize e-learning resources for instructional delivery. Based on the findings, it was concluded that inadequate utilization of e-learning resources in the programme is a major contributory factor to the ineffective duty performance of the products in offices of the current era.

Olutola, Olatoye and Olatoye (2021) conducted a study on assessing the impediments to e-learning utilization by higher institution students. Findings revealed that all the fifteen impediments investigated in this study affect the e-learning utilization by higher institution students in Katsina State, Nigeria in varying degrees.

Ela (2021) conducted a study on the utilization of e-learning facilities for effective instructional process in tertiary institutions, Rivers State. Findings from the study showed that there is significant difference between lecture and students rating regarding on the proficiency of lecturers and that of students in the utilization of e-learning facilities in tertiary institutions.

Oladeji and Sikiru-Issa (2021) conducted a study on awareness and utilization of e-learning technologies in teaching and learning of business education courses in universities in Kwara State. The findings of this study showed that lectures and students are aware of synchronous e-learning technologies in teaching and learning of business education courses.

Gaps in Empirical Review

The existing empirical research focused on the utilization of virtual learning applications in e-learning delivery within public universities in Enugu State. However, there is a gap in the literature that this current study aims to address. This gap pertains to the availability of virtual learning applications, the integration of these applications into instructional planning, instructional delivery, evaluation of instruction, and the strategies employed by public universities to integrate virtual learning applications into students' degree programmes. These specific areas have not been thoroughly investigated by any researcher in the study area, as far as the researcher has observed. Therefore, conducting this study is crucial to fill this gap in knowledge.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher adopted a descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey research design, according to Nworgu (2015), is defined as one which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from a few people or items regarded as being representative of the entire group. This design was appropriate because a representative sample of the total population was used to collect data from the respondents.

Area of the Study

The area of the study was Enugu State. Enugu State is made up of 17 local government areas. There are six Education Zones in Enugu State which include Agbani, Awgu, Enugu, Nsukka, Obolo-afor and Udi. Enugu State is bounded to the East by Ebonyi State, to the west by Anambra State, to the North by Kogi and Benue

States. The inhabitants of Enugu State are mostly civil servants, businessmen, farmers and artisans. The language of the people of Enugu State is Igbo and most of them are involved in agriculture and civil service. The choice of Enugu State for this study is because the researcher is interested in knowing the utilization of virtual learning applications in e-learning delivery in public universities in Enugu State.

Population for the Study

The population for the study was 5437 which comprised 839 academic staff and 4598 final year students in University of Nigeria, Nsukka and Enugu State University of Science and Technology, ESUT (2022/2023 session).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for the study was 523 copies (75 from lecturers and 448 from final year students). In order to draw the sample size for the study, the researcher used stratified, proportionate random sampling techniques. For each of stratum (University), ten percent (10%) of the lecturers and students were randomly sampled. This is in line with Uzoagulu (2013), who posited that when the population for a known study is in thousands the researcher can make use of a desired percent for the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was a researcher structured questionnaire titled “Utilization of Virtual Learning Applications in E-Learning Delivery Questionnaire (UVLAELDQ)”. The questionnaire had three sections, A, B and C. Section A focused on the bio-data of the respondents (lecturers and students), section B focused on the information on the availability of virtual learning applications and section C focused on perception of lecturers and students on the integration of virtual learning applications into instructional planning, instructional delivery and evaluation of instruction. It had 62 items that were built in five clusters. Cluster 1 had 14 items on the availability of virtual learning applications. Cluster 2 had 11 items on the integration of utilization of virtual learning applications into instructional planning. Cluster 3 had 10 items on the integration of virtual learning applications into instructional delivery. Cluster 4 had 13 items on the integration of virtual learning applications into evaluation of instruction. Cluster 5 had 14 items on the strategies adopted in the integration of virtual learning applications for the students’ degree programmes. The researcher used a 4-point rating scale for cluster B2 -5. Cluster 1 had response options of available and not available. Meanwhile, clusters 2 – 5 had response options of Strongly Agree (SA) - 4 points, Agree (A) - 3 points, Disagree (D) - 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1 point. An introductory letter stating the reasons for the study was attached to the instrument for the respondents (Appendix A).

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was validated by three research validates. The three specialists were from the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education, Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu. The researcher presented copies of the purposes, research questions as well as the hypotheses to the research validates. The specialists were asked to advise with regards to the adequacy of items, relevance and appropriateness of the items, grammatical and structural errors as well as sentence construction.

The 62 items survived the validation process. The researcher utilized their corrections in improving the research instrument. This was done and their observations and corrections guided the production of the final draft that was used for the study (See Appendix B).

Reliability of the Instrument

To ensure the reliability of the instrument, it was trial tested on 12 lecturers and 28 students in public universities in Anambra State. Anambra State was used because the two groups of respondents in Anambra State shared similar characteristics with their counterparts in Enugu State in terms of school administration. To ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument, the researcher used Cronbach alpha statistic. The choice of Cronbach Alpha statistic was that it helps to determine the internal consistency of average correlation of items in a survey instrument in order to gauge its reliability. The computation yielded .79 for cluster 1, .82 for cluster 2, .81 for cluster 3, .80 for cluster 4 and .81 for cluster 5. The instrument had an overall reliability index of .81 which indicated that the instrument is reliable and, therefore, was used for data collection in this study (Appendix C).

Method of Data Collection

The researcher with the help of three research assistants administered the instrument on the respondents (lecturers and students). The research assistants assisted in the administration and retrieval of the copies of questionnaire to the respondents. The research assistants were briefed by the researcher in a one-day interactive session. They were taught on how to be polite to the respondents as well as how to answer questions if there is need. However, out of the 544 copies of questionnaire administered, the researcher with his researcher assistants retrieved 523 copies (75 from lecturers and 448 from final year students) which resulted to 96.14 percent return rate.

Method of Data Analyses

The researcher used frequency and percentages to answer research question 1, but used mean scores and standard deviations to answer research questions 2-5. The null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic at .05 level of significance. In rating the mean, each response option had a numerical value based on real limit of numbers: SA = 3.50-4.00; A = 2.50-3.49; D = 1.50-2.49; SD = 0.00-1.49 for research questions 2-5. The interpretation of the test of hypotheses was based on the significance (sig.) values from the SPSS output. The null hypothesis was not rejected when the probability values were greater than .05, but was rejected when the probability values were less than .05, indicating a statistically significant result in the latter case.

Data Analyses and Result Presentation

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers and students on their perception on the integration of the virtual learning applications that are adequately made available into instructional planning in the students' courses as they pursuit their degree programmes in public universities.

Table 1: Summary of t-test Analysis on the Mean ratings of lecturers and students on their perception on the integration of the virtual learning applications available into instructional planning

Variables	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	p-value	Decision
Lecturers	75	2.89	.85	521	.096	Do not Reject Ho ₁
Students	448	2.81	.82			

The data presented in Table 1 indicates that at 521 degrees of freedom, the p-value obtained was .096, exceeding the predetermined significance level of .05 for this study. As a result, the null hypothesis was not rejected, suggesting that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers and students regarding their perception on the integration of the virtual learning applications that are adequately made available into instructional planning in the students' courses as they pursuit their degree programmes in public universities.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers and students regarding the integration of virtual learning applications into instructional delivery for degree programmes at public universities.

Table 2: Summary of t-test Analysis on the Mean ratings of lecturers and students on their perception on the integration of the virtual learning applications that are adequately made available into instructional delivery

Variables	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Lecturers	75	2.83	.86	521	.089	Do not Reject Ho ₂
Students	448	2.76	.86			

The data presented in Table 2 indicates that at 521 degrees of freedom, the p-value obtained was .096, which is greater than the significance level of .05 for this study. As a result, the null hypothesis was not rejected, suggesting that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers and students regarding their perception on the integration of the virtual learning applications that are adequately made available into instructional delivery in the students' courses as they pursuit their degree programmes in public universities.

Summary of Findings

The following are the findings of the study:

1. Virtual learning applications are not adequately made available for the lecturers and students' utilization for e-learning delivery in public universities.
2. The respondents viewed the integration of virtual learning applications into instructional planning in public universities positively.

Conclusion

In conclusion, despite the insufficient availability of virtual learning applications for e-learning delivery in public universities, the respondents expressed a positive perception towards their integration into instructional planning, delivery, and evaluation. This indicates a readiness among lecturers and students to embrace virtual learning tools in the academic setting. Moreover, the respondents displayed optimism towards the strategies employed by public universities in Enugu State for integrating virtual learning applications into degree programmes. These findings suggest a potential for further development and implementation of virtual learning technologies to enhance the educational experience within public universities. However, addressing the lack of accessibility to such applications remains a crucial aspect for effective e-learning delivery in these institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Universities management should provide comprehensive training sessions for lecturers and students on utilizing virtual learning applications effectively.
2. University stakeholders should encourage further exploration and integration of virtual learning applications into instructional planning through workshops and seminars.

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